

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Bakaev N.B.

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378840>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st March 2022

Accepted: 10th March 2022

Online: 17th March 2022

KEY WORDS

goals, problems, tasks, teaching methods, motivation, means of communication, information technologies, Internet, activity approach, computerization.

ABSTRACT

This article is aimed at methodological analysis and identification of the most pressing issues related to teaching a foreign language in educational institutions. Teaching foreign languages in the era of globalization has its own characteristics and problems: first of all, it is a change in the content of teaching a foreign language, methods and means of teaching in accordance with the requirements of modern society. The most important and relevant aspect of effective foreign language teaching in our time is the use of Internet information resources, their integration into the educational process for the productive solution of a number of didactic tasks in the classroom. Learning a foreign language in modern realities should be carried out in the course of performing productive types of work - listening to foreign language speech, reading texts, writing and speaking. All these activities are considered not as an end in themselves, but as a way for students to solve specific personally important problems and tasks.

The topical issue today is what should be a foreign language lesson in modern conditions. The goals and content of education are changing, new means and technologies of education are emerging, but no matter what reforms are carried out, the lesson remains the eternal and main form of education. No matter what innovations are introduced, participants in the educational process meet only in the classroom: the teacher and the student.

The goal of teaching a foreign language today is no longer achievable by simply

communicating a certain amount of knowledge that students must memorize and reproduce. Simultaneously with arming with knowledge and on its basis, it is necessary to teach students the methods of cognition and practical activity that mankind has developed.

Main part

A foreign language lesson has a special specificity that a foreign language teacher cannot ignore. At present, the global goal of mastering a foreign language is considered to be familiarization with a different

culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. This goal is achieved through the formation of the ability to intercultural communication. It is teaching, organized on the basis of tasks of a communicative nature, teaching foreign language communication, using all the tasks and techniques necessary for this, that is a distinctive feature of a foreign language lesson.

Training aimed at the formation of communicative competence can only take place in the conditions of a personality-oriented and activity approach. Learning to communicate should take place in the course of performing productive types of work - listening to foreign language speech, reading texts, writing and speaking. All these activities are considered not as an end in themselves, but as a way for students to solve specific personally important problems and tasks. The personality-oriented (personality-activity) approach is based on taking into account the individual characteristics of the trainees, who are considered as individuals with their own characteristics, inclinations and interests.

Training in accordance with this approach involves:

- independence of students in the learning process, which is often expressed in the definition of the goals and objectives of the course by the students themselves, in the choice of methods that are preferable for them;
- reliance on the existing knowledge of students, on his experience;
- taking into account the sociocultural characteristics of students and their

lifestyle, encouraging the desire to be "oneself";

- taking into account the emotional state of students, as well as their moral, ethical and moral values;

- purposeful formation of learning skills, characteristic of a particular student learning strategies;

- redistribution of roles in the educational process: limiting the leading role of the teacher, assigning the teacher the functions of an assistant, consultant, adviser

In a modern foreign language lesson, students, together with the teacher, carry out joint activities. The teacher becomes the organizer of the educational, collectively distributed activities of students, an equal participant in the dialogue. The teacher leads to awareness of the problem, shows, reminds, consults. He creates a situation of success, empathizes, encourages, inspires confidence, stimulates, forms the motives for teaching, shows encouraging exactingness, coordinates, strengthens the authority of the student among his comrades. Students set and solve educational problems, control and evaluate their activities, compare, analyze, classify, model, communicate, defend their point of view, listen and hear classmates, actively interact, plan and control joint activities.

Modern approaches are of great importance in the organization of the learning process, but despite this, there are also some shortcomings, the elimination of which can significantly improve its quality, as well as be a good help for the teacher in the implementation of modern approaches to the organization of the learning process.

With the use of computers, this is excluded, since the visualization required in the lessons and the situations on the monitors are quite real - the "images" move, speak English, ask questions, etc. Some teachers may ask: won't the lesson turn from creative work into something entertaining? No, because in order to get a good grade when working with a computer, a student has to work creatively. He does everything with joy, and the teacher has to purchase the necessary electronic textbooks and make a selection of the necessary situations from them, as well as print out additional questions and texts and transfer them to all computers so that at a certain point in the lesson, students can sit down at certain computers, find and open desired folder in "My Documents", perform, for example, a listening or reading test. It's a lot of work, but it pays off. The joy of learning - that's what gives the use of computers in the classroom. And this, in turn, along with the development of thinking leads to the development of initiative speech.

Each person has an internal motive aimed at cognitive activity. The task of the teacher is to contribute in every possible way to the development of this motive, not to let it fade away. Now there is a wide variety of modern multimedia programs, where you can find enough exercises for students of all ages and different knowledge. Sounds, words, phrases and sentences are perceived by students by ear and visually. Students have the opportunity to observe articulation movements on the computer screen and perceive the correct intonation by ear. At the same time, due to the rather high imitative abilities of

students, the correct samples are imprinted in their memory.

The computerization of our society is calling for life and the emergence of more and more people who want and can use these smart machines in everyday life. Computers make life easier and more interesting. After all, if with the help of this machine within an hour or two you can attend training courses on the Internet in any subject of the school and extracurricular programs, see the world in its current state and diversity, communicate with a huge mass of different people and gain access to libraries, museums and exhibitions that one can only dream of, then there really is no better means for self-development and individual education and self-education. The use of Internet resources and computer presentations in English lessons.

Now everyone understands that the Internet has enormous information capabilities and no less impressive services. The Internet creates a unique opportunity for foreign language learners to use authentic texts, listen and communicate with native speakers. It is important to decide for what purposes we are going to use its capabilities and resources. For instance:

- to include the materials of the network in the content of the lesson,
- for students to independently search for information as part of the work on the project,

Using the information resources of the Internet, it is possible, by integrating them into the educational process, to more

effectively solve a number of didactic tasks in the lesson:

- to develop reading skills and abilities, directly using the materials of the network of varying degrees of complexity,

- improve listening skills based on authentic Internet audio texts, also prepared by the teacher accordingly,

improve the skills of monologue and dialogic utterance on the basis of a problematic discussion of the materials presented by the teacher or one of the students of the network,

- replenish your vocabulary, both active and passive, with the vocabulary of a modern foreign language, reflecting a certain stage in the development of the culture of the people, the social and political structure of society,

- get acquainted with cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette, especially the speech behavior of various peoples in terms of communication, cultural features, traditions of the country of the language being studied.

Conclusion

In conclusion I would like to add that it is also optimal to create multimedia Power Point presentations. The use of computer presentations in the classroom allows you to introduce new lexical, country-specific

material in the most exciting form, the principle of visibility is implemented, which contributes to a solid assimilation of information. Independent creative work of students to create computer presentations is the best way to expand the stock of active vocabulary.

The tasks of education modernization cannot be solved without the optimal implementation of information technologies in all its spheres. The use of information technology gives impetus to the development of new forms and content of traditional activities of students, which leads to their mastering and implementation at a higher level. Working with a computer should be organized in such a way that from the very first lessons of the initial stage of education it becomes a powerful psychological and pedagogical means of forming a need-motivational plan for students' activities, a means of maintaining and further developing their interest in the subject being studied. Properly organized work of students with a computer can contribute, in particular, to the growth of their cognitive and communicative interest, which in turn will contribute to the activation and expansion of the opportunities for independent work of students in mastering the English language, both in the classroom and outside of school hours.

References:

1. Schukin A.N. Textbook for teachers and students. – M.: Philomatis, 2004. – p. 416.
2. Hutchinson T., Waters; A. English for Specific Purposes: a learning-centered approach. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005. – 183 p.
3. Polyakov O.G. Theoretical and practical aspects of the development of profile-oriented programs in English // IYaSh. - 2004. - No. 7. - S. 12-16.

4. Swales J. Genre Analysis: English in academic and research settings / J. Swales. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990. – 272 p.
5. Lewis M. & Hill J. Practical Techniques for Language Teaching. - London: Longman, 1992. - 143 p.
6. Tsaturova I.A. The paradigm of language education in higher education in the 21st century is “teaching students to learn” // Education and Society. - 2004. - No. 4. [Electronic pecypc]. URL: http://education.recom.m/3_2004/46.html
7. Abramova I.G. Active teaching methods in higher education. – M.: Gardarika, 2008. – 368 p.
8. Rogers T. Methodology in the New Millennium // English Teaching Forum. - 2000. - Vol. 38. - No 2. - P. 2-13.
9. Tosun V.C. A New Challenge in the Methodology of the Post-Method Era // Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies. – October 2009. – Vol. 5. - No. 2. - P. 10-15.
10. Nuttal C. Teaching Reading Skills in a Foreign Language. (2nd edn.). – Oxford: Heinemann, 1996.